

INTELLECTUAL AND IMMATERIAL BANK

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

BY WISE JESTER

ANNA ZAYTSEVA

wisejester@intellectualandimmaterialbank.com

July-August 2021, Oslo, Norway

Background story

It was March 2010. I was walking down a street in Sweden, and a man with an obvious foreign background looked at me in a way I found unacceptable.

Options to behave:

- to start/join a political party against foreigners
- to join a feministic movement
- to complain

1)

f
r
o
m
s
o
c
i
a
l

- to solve that problem intelligently by learning its complexity seriously
- to set up a hypothesis: What if there existed a blind system for showing capacities of people and needs in them at organizations?
- to imagine a solution IIB and describe it on 50 pages, with graphs
- to take a PhD in Management of Information Systems for managing it
- to gain experience at an innovation-support center
- to attend workshops by the European Commission about the free movement of people, talent, hybrid jobs, diversity and inclusion
- to found a startup and execute the solution using humor as innovation
- to pivot IIB for inclusion of diverse healthy and spectrum minds

2)

The depth of the wicked, complex problem

How often people superficially judge: in 75% of natives report misjudging others at least once a month or more¹

How many people are conformists: 65% of people act under the pressure of social expectations²

How many change processes fail: from 50% to 90%³

Why thinking is difficult: unconscious autopilot thinking can process 11 million bits of information/sec. and consumes only 25% of energy, whereas deeper thinking can only process 40 bits of information/sec. and consumes 75% of energy⁴

Correlation between language and intelligence: none⁵

Why inclusion and diversity programs fail: because they are based on quota of visual criteria such as age, gender, ethnicities, social classes, income levels, and other backgrounds; they lack long-term plan, structure and commitment⁶

How much of investment in organizational performance is wasted: from 80% to 90%⁷

What HR say about organizations: “organizations are chaoses”⁸

1. Elizabeth Thornton, 19 January 2015, How often do you judge people unfairly? What is the cost?: The tendency is common, the consequences are significant, Psychology Today
2. Stanley Milgram, Oct. 1963, Behavioral study of obedience, The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology, Vol. 67(4)
3. Jon Ivar Johansen, 2019, Endringskoden
4. John A. Bargh, 2007, Social psychology and the unconscious: The automaticity of higher mental processes
5. Janet Gibson, 2019, An introduction to the psychology of humor
6. Erika Johnson, 29 March 2021, Top 4 reasons diversity and inclusion programs fail
7. Mary Broad, 2005, Beyond transfer of training: Engaging systems to improve performance
8. Interview with a HR consultant and partner at a big HR organization, March 2020, Oslo, Norway

The depth of the wicked, complex problem

How many people hate their jobs: 85%, but what keeps them from leaving are responsibility, lack of job opportunities, fear of being wrong, fear of the unknown, a seniority complex, and salary⁸

What job coaches recommend: “sell yourself!”¹⁰

How existing algorithms assess your suitability for work: “Most matching engines [...] generate [...] their recommendations on [...] behavioral data, like how often a user responds to messages or interacts with job postings.”¹¹

How many jobs will change beyond recognition because of development: “up to 47% within the next 25 years”¹² or more!

Creativity is difficult to evaluate and quantify, so hybrid-knowledge future-oriented jobs remain exotic: no universal income for creative professionals, what marginalizes them and leads to dehumanization of industries¹³

What technological progress and globalization require from labor and thinking: intellectual diversity and intellectual inclusion for hybrid-knowledge professions like operator of automated tools, healthcare engineer, robot dispatcher, asteroid miner, professional gamer, space clinician, image consultant, civilian drone controller, exobiologist, etc.¹⁴

8. Clarisse Levitan, Staff Squared HR, 3 December 2019, Why 85% of people hate their jobs

9. Interview with 2 job coaches, November 2017, Oslo, Norway

11. Sheridan Wall, Hilke Schellmann, 23 June 2021, LinkedIn's job-matching AI was biased. The company's solution? More AI, MIT Technology Review

12. Philip Perry, 24 December 2016, 47% of jobs will vanish in the next 25 years say Oxford University researchers, Big Think

13. Jordan Peterson, YouTube Channel “National Gallery of Canada”, video “Lectures: Exploring the Psychology of Creativity”, dated 27 April 2017

14. Workshops by the European Commission about the future of labor, emerging jobs and skills, 2016-present

WE USED TO DO THE HELLFIRE AND HARD-LABOR THING, BUT NOW WE JUST HOLD PEOPLE TO THEIR OWN STANDARDS. WAY MORE ENTERTAINING.

kevin-stafford.weebly.com

Wise Jester

Password must contain a symbol, a number, an emotional arc, a centralized theme, a big set piece, a male lead "struggling w/inner demons" & a strong female character.

Why is humor an innovative solution here?

Humor is a special area of cognitive science. Humor is about **clashing situations** that relate. Brain “solves” a joke and **rewards itself** with a smile or laugh, which cannot be faked. Humor is based on re-composition of what people know and can synthesize, when they “**crack**” the code of a joke by getting it. Considering that jokes demonstrate a rich diversity, individual appreciation of humor is naturally **unique**. To collaborate is a process and a skill, exploring a balance between **certainty and uncertainty**, compatibility and challenge. **Humor code-cracking qualities** give a great clue about it!

Jim Morrison, The Doors:

“I've noticed that when people are joking, they're usually dead serious, and when they're serious, they're usually pretty funny.”

Your capacities

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon**.

While thinking, you are rather after **imagination**.
You tend to react immediately to **social signals**.
You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts**.

- preferred comfort zones
 - Low-pressure contexts
 - Contexts with high uncertainty
 - Collectivistic environments
 - High-pressure contexts
 - Independent genre
- instant-th. triggers
 - Social signals
 - Cognitive signals
 - Emotional signals
 - Knowledge
 - Focused aim
- deep-th. triggers
 - Solidarity with the others
 - Imagination
 - Coming up with alternatives
 - Faster taking the new into practice
- capacities for transformation
 - Having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis
 - Proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon
 - Breaking the old things down faster
 - Standing for flat collaboration of hybrid competencies

Needs of your collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck**.

Your collaboration may experience **ignoring uniqueness**.
Your collaboration might be overlooking **how the others feel**.
Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by expecting **individual initiative**.

- disruption of comfort
 - Pressuring the members
 - Demanding clarity and plan
 - Expecting individual initiative
 - Slowing down for well-ordered actions
 - Accountability and transparency
- tendency to ignore
 - The socially accepted
 - Facts and numbers
 - How others feel
 - Siloed thinking
 - Being too dispersed
- intellectual depth
 - Ignoring uniqueness
 - Being too down-to-earth
 - Structures and processes that are stuck
 - Fear of difference and novelty
 - Seeing the big picture
- needs in transformation
 - Obvious needs in new, unknown ideas
 - Degree of inner passion of the member
 - Potential for synergic collaboration

What can the humor module of IIB do?

In IIB, humor “does” unique user-data generation, computed to show the professionals their **own unique way of thinking** where **contexts collide**. Properly argued and anchored in Humor Science, the module shows you your instinctive (unconscious, autopilot) thinking and deeper (conscious aware) thinking, beautifully theorized by Daniel Kahneman, who got a Nobel prize in behavioral economics for that. The theory was further developed by a humor scientist Larry Ventis, and his peers in Cognitive science, Linguistics, Psychology, Behaviorism, and more. Also, that theory was accurately applied by Jon Ivar Johansen to explore **change processes in organizations, starting from individuals**. Compiled in a unique way with practice, the elements of the accumulated knowledge emerged into a **synthesized, relationship-intensive** module in IIB, full of mathematical calculations, created and applied by the founder of Wise Jester. Mathematically and computationally, IIB considers the tendency of the human mind to **equilibrium** and, also, **values its natural “edge of chaos”**, including such features as **imagination and spontaneity**.

A permanent link to a document with the relevant science extracts:
<https://zenodo.org/record/4724974>

Meanwhile, the problem of lack of meaning and vision at work is growing...

Suggested for you **Facebook** **Print-screened: 24 July 2021**

CNBC International

Leading experts on happiness on the after effects of quitting your job and how to prepare to ensure success.

CNBC.COM
People are quitting their jobs in record numbers—here's why it might not make you any happier
fact → **bias of organizational interest, again**

 1.4K 377 comments 279 shares

 Brett Thiele
It worked out for me. I resigned from my job after 8 years when the Operations Manager told me; "it isn't my job to show appreciation or give positive reinforcement". Thankfully, I found a company that has already respected me more in the first month than the other did in all 8 years. I should have made the move 5 years ago.

Know your value. Because you are worth it.

Like · Reply · 2 d · Edited 244

 Amanda Lovejoy
This is a good thing for our country. Instead of a job shortage, we have an employee shortage. It means that jobs will actually have to compete for employees, instead of employees desperate to be hired. They will have to up benefits, up pay, and provide positive working environments for employees, which was sorely lacking in the US pre-COVID. This is the way it should be.

Like · Reply · 2 d 152

 Tony Williams
The thing that will drive me away from a job is a bad boss. If the boss is abusive, unsupportive, or unknowledgeable, I'm out. A bad work environment or culture will make me leave. I like to be in an environment with positive people who work as a team to achieve a goal and get the work done. I'm not into clicks or office politics. Finally, at this stage in my career, the commute time is very important. The two hour commutes are over for me. I have been offered wonderful jobs that I had to turn down because of the commute. Those days are over for me unless I have absolutely no other options.

Like · Reply · 2 d · Edited 23

 A.L. Savage
This article is meant to manipulate people into staying a battery for large corporations because people are waking up and becoming entrepreneurs in record numbers now days and actually being successful at it myself included. I'm handing in my notice REAL soon.

Like · Reply · 1 d 36

IIB places individuals and collaborations on one plane, where either side can choose another, and their visions are mutually presented.

Wise Jester

...while the conventional problem of standing out and fitting in remains!

Jordan Peterson about Robert Sapolsky's research about zebras:

If you understand the story, you understand absolutely everything about human beings. Lions are camouflaged: they are of the same color as the grass. Zebras are black and white. But there isn't a zebra, there is a herd of zebras. The zebras are camouflaged against the herd. Biologists go out and study zebras: they make a note, and they look up and they think – which collection of black and white stripes was that zebra? If you look away from a zebra down and back up, you don't know what you're looking at. The stripes don't outline a zebra, and they camouflage the zebra perfectly against the herd. The biologists painted a part on one of the zebras. Guess what happens to the zebra? The lions eat it. **The lions cannot hunt a single zebra down unless they can identify it.** And so, they go for a little one or the one that is limp, that is for the weak. But they want the juicy ones. **You make yourself colorful, you stand out – the lions will kill you.**

Source: YouTube channel “National Gallery of Canada”, video “Lectures: Exploring the Psychology of Creativity” with Jordan Peterson (April 27, 2017)

Hui Liao and Elizabeth M. Campbell “Killing High Performers With Teamwork: Why Hotshots Must Be Handled With Care In Group Settings” (November 15, 2017)

Organizations hire people who stand out and then tell them to fit in. ... Research shows that 30 percent of high performers report lack of engagement, while 25 percent expect to work elsewhere within a year. ... High performers can threaten their peers. They can shake up the status quo by challenging assumptions, asking uncomfortable questions, and increasing performance standards. ... Colleagues label star performers as “freaks” or “geniuses” to depersonalize and isolate them. ... Punishing high performers makes sense because they represent a real or potential threat to scarce resources. ... Staying close to high performers makes sense because ... high performers make others look good when teams share credit for a job well done. Their peers ... target them for both sabotage and support. ... Experiencing both friendliness and hostility from the same source is even more toxic than experiencing negativity alone.

When given an opportunity to anonymously vote out one from their group, the peers tend to vote out those, who were dragging their group forward.

The Wiley Handbook of Genius, ed. by Dean Keith Simonton (2014)

That is why IIB delivers blind connections, unique and meaningful for the users, and in no silos.

What is IIB by Wise Jester?

Visionary and deployed, IIB is:

a blind network to facial data (names, socio-political statuses, and any “quota” data like age, gender...)

for independent professional as the main user unit who initiates and approves all interactions

represented holistically in visualization of own deeper- and instant thinking

where their collaborations are stipulated by shared visions

and preferred compositions of hybrid knowledge for

training risk- and collaboration skill

valuing imagination

via humor

UN Global Compact Norway

3,594 followers

Promoted

Unicus ansetter kun mennesker med Asperger. Statnett mener kompetansen er vanskelig å få tak i, og kan bidra til å spare Statnett for flerfoldige millioner. Hør hvordan Unicus mener at asperger er et konkurransefortrinn som krever lite tilrettelegging.

Faglig påfyll

Asperger som konkurransefortrinn

FN FREMTIDENS NÆRINGS- LIV

Asperger som konkurransefortrinn

fremtidensnaringsliv.no

[Learn more](#)

How are intellectual diversity and inclusion being approached in the new socio-economic reality?

For communication and interest-based community-building in no facial disclosure [bottom-up]: Reddit, Telegram, Signal, Discord

For economic empowerment of independent professionals [bottom-up]: Upwork, Fiverr, Toptal, Freelancer.com, Insolvo

In organizational interests [top-down, conventionally]: HR

As specialized companies [emerging phenomenon]: Unicus

IIB is blind, showing uniqueness of thinking in deeper and autopilot thinking [+ more] of independent professionals, and needs in it at collaborations, in mutual compatibility and challenge, and at least 3 out of 5 knowledge areas, where shared visions have the last say

Anna Andreyevna
30 November 2019 · 🌐

"All the most beautiful in the world is being made by the narcissists, all the most interesting – by the schizoids, the kindest – by the depressive, the impossible – by the psychopaths. Healthy people make almost no contribution to history."

Gannushkin, P.B. (1933) Manifestations of psychopathies: statics, dynamics, systematic aspects

Picture: Something freaky, but surprisingly popular since 1510, by Hieronymus Bosch

Music: Agatha Christie "Like on War": <https://youtu.be/3421MMqetHc>

"...The battle's over, the fire's extinguished –
And nothing's left... But we're living,
We got lucky – no matter what!"

Andrius Guzaitis, Alix Chen and 4 others
2 comments

Like Comment Share

Maria Lorenza Garcia
How about the autistic?... the best science ? hihi
Like · Reply · 1 y

Anna Andreyevna
I can not claim regarding science, but in Norway there is an IT company, entirely consisting of people with autism. The company is called Unicus. What may pleasantly surprise immediately is their concern about the preferences of their website visitors. No matter

Pivoting: IIB as a social welfare solution for intellectual inclusion and diversity

On July 19, when I was typing #speechdefect, a friend Christian, colorblind and dyslexic, from a tech labor union, wrote to me that he talked about IIB to his spectrum friends. They use Discord and Signal to communicate and get involved, but that does not bring them the desired results. And they got genuinely excited when he told them about IIB.

Spectrum people may have trouble with irony, though. However, irony as humor that requires empathy is only one part of the IIB solution. Other humor forms too are embedded in IIB from the start. Normal people appreciate irony easily, and so, everyone has a fair place on IIB.

IIB assists compatibility among individuals and their self-organized groups in autopilot and deeper thinking [+ more], hybrid-knowledge compositions and shared visions. With its blindness, IIB solves the problems of minds being superficially judged by other humans and their groups (slides 3, 4).

Pivoting: IIB as a social welfare solution for emerging professions

On IIB, intuitive introverts, and **normal**, kind, sensitive people, and **spectrum** people, or people with any specific intellectual traits that may fail the first impression, avoid the meaningless challenge of “selling themselves” to a group, person, or HR.

IIB empowers people to **initiate** or **join** hybrid-knowledge or **STEAM** projects, or any collaborations where their qualities would be of **advantage**, and **visionary** projects where their ways of feeling are not misjudged as “**risky**” by those of the normal distribution. Their fresh insight and **morality** access collaborations on IIB. IIB promotes strengths of the **minds in diversity**. In contrast to psychometrics, IIB shows no extremes.

The users of IIB learn **risk taking**, assisted, and train their **collaboration** and **communication skill**, **validated** by becoming an author or a member of any self-emerging collaboration, with hybrid knowledge and shared, future-oriented visions.

Anna Andreyevna

12 October 2016 · 🌐

What a highly useful and promising meeting (and two more) at the European Commission! 😊 Asteroid miner, professional gamer, space clinician, image consultant, civilian drone controller, exobiologist, etc. 😊 The degree of my joy is immeasurable – I can't stop smiling 😊 being very serious 😊

Gianni Tee, Robert Booker and 4 others

1 comment

Like

Comment

Share

Brent Schneeman

1

Like · Reply · 4 y

Write a comment...

Who are the users and beneficiaries of IIB?

Professionals who are:

after meaningful, visionary involvements (those who want more than a predictable life: to have more written about their deeds on their headstones than just their names and lifespans, when they die)

authors and owners of long-term purposeful processes, requiring from 3 and more knowledge areas

bright, kind people, who are not willing to fight in political games to receive recognition

people, who hope not for selfies, but are rather passionate about doing epic shit

lighthearted people, normally scoring high in openness to experience

intuitive introverts in their shells and when they speak up

turned down as “overqualified” or white crows

life-long learners and gifted

spectrum people

creators

Why would we need IIB for these people?

for social and intellectual diversity

for social and intellectual inclusion

for training risk-taking skill, assisted

for training collaboration skill, assisted

for humanization of business processes

for humanization of technological processes

for emergence of hybrid-knowledge professions

for encouragement of imagination and creativity

APPLIED RIGHT AWAY

**IIB by Wise Jester is a solution
for intellectual inclusion and diversity,
and emerging professions, targeting visions**

adaptive, self-emerging collaborations, welfare

mutual compatibility and challenges

game-based choice-making

quantified imagination

visualizations

humor

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

Here are some pictures to set the mood. Just click them through! :)

Here are some pictures to set the mood. Just click them through! :)

[Team Wise Jester](#)

[What IIB is](#)

[News about IIB](#)

[Contact us](#)

[Log in](#)

The king divided his kingdom among his three sons. "Fabulous!" said the fourth.

32/36

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

[Team Wise Jester](#)

[What IIB is](#)

[News about IIB](#)

[Contact us](#)

[Log in](#)

The longer the doorbell rings, the more I'm not at home.

21/36

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

[Team Wise Jester](#)

[What IIB is](#)

[News about IIB](#)

[Contact us](#)

[Log in](#)

To the one who will rid me of megalomania, I will give Great Britain.

9/36

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

[BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL](#)

[BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION](#)

Team Wise Jester

What IIB is

News about IIB

Contact us

Log in

What are the domains of your professional interests formal and informal? Choose 5.
You can select what have you studied, worked with and are curios of, and what you simply love.

- Physics
- Engineering
- Statistics
- Math
- XR
- Robotics
- Coding
- Regulation
- Economics
- Gaming
- Entrepreneurship
- User experience
- Social work
- Writing
- Music
- Complex systems
- Hybrid innovation
- Communication
- Arts
- Sports
- Medicine
- Blockchain
- Environment
- Audiovisual works

DONE!

these can always be enriched

You own your data. You get a punk "mohawk" of your intellectual uniqueness, which is your only picture that other users can "see". You use your mohawk to build up your de facto collaborations or to attract those. IIB is a blind gamified network. The last say between you and others will have a shared vision.

BEGIN AS AN INDEPENDENT PROFESSIONAL

BEGIN AS AN AUTHOR OF A COLLABORATION

Your strongest capacity for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon.**

While thinking, you are rather after **imagination.**

You tend to react immediately to **social signals.**

You prefer working in **low-pressure contexts.**

Pitched: I am a dreamer and doer who wants to build intelligence-intensive mechatronic solutions of tomorrow.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkytq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**

While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**

The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**

The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, gaming, statistics.**

The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics.**

Pitched: I am crazy about math and physics, because we can make even more new solutions if we better understand Mother Nature!

Username: sjaqqkgjagd652o1hwekhsjgkah82o2tyuq2jgdqhgwhfqkjh

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **emotional signals.**

While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **imagination.**

The main strength of this person is in **having a discovery mindset, capable of synthesis.**

The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **engineering, entrepreneurship, statistics.**

The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **physics, robotics.**

Pitched: My main interest is emerging business models, and I would love to join a startup that works on a highly unique idea.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: qjgksjdjahgdw82632jgahfwhqjt2i1gsgdj1tidbj2tksvghj187ejs

This person is favorably complementing you in response to new situations by being rather sensitive to **cognitive signals.**

While thinking before doing, this person also goes for **focused aim.**

The main strength of this person is in **breaking the old things down faster.**

The competencies, which this person shares with your request, are primarily: **math, engineering.**

The unique competencies, which this person can bring in, are: **complex systems, robotics, coding.**

Pitched: Robots are my everything. I worked in industrial robotics, and now I want to build a humanoid of my own.

Needs of my collaboration

Your collaboration may have a challenge with **structures and processes that are stuck**.

Your collaboration may experience **being too dispersed**.

Your collaboration might be overlooking the **socially accepted**.

Your collaboration disrupts comfort zones by **pressuring the members**.

Pitched: Our team is looking for a bright developer who understands the social complexity around emerging technologies and can work fast.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: jwgejay2731kjqhwmai2u01lkqajy2g1jhqf62reamo03egh120

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **faster taking the new into practice**.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **collectivistic environments**.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **solidarity with the others**.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics**.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **statistics, physics, engineering**.

Pitched: I am a Java developer, and I am available to become a part of a new environment. I love travelling too.

Username: sjghwja721klwjka89q2kajwhdjba827jhwekq3ryhjqqh62jq2g

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **proposing idiotic ideas, which will be right soon**.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **high-pressure contexts**.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **imagination**.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **xr, robotics**.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, entrepreneurship, engineering**.

Pitched: I am developing a new type of digital wallets. I am looking for collaborations that develop respective user applications.

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

Username: dshwi363kshkqtq65w33sd2kshu289hksqmbg891hjkshqlqqk

The strongest capacity of this person for making change is **breaking the old things down faster**.

To balance your work style, this person prefers working in **contexts with high uncertainty**.

When thinking over something in depth, this person goes for **focused aim**.

The competencies of this person, which you requested for your collaboration, are primarily: **coding, robotics**.

The unique competencies, which this person can bring into your collaboration, are: **complex systems, math, engineering**.

Pitched: My dream is to create machines that talk!

INTRODUCE YOURSELF

+ a complex chat is being added

Me contacting individuals [independent professionals]:

- On my behalf _____
- On behalf of my collaboration _____

Me contacting collaborations

Me being contacted:

- By other individuals [independent professionals]
- By collaborations

+ Conversations in my collaborations

+ My everybody

What can that give to you? That is the fun part: surprises.

But! You must be a person of integrity and respect other people. Don't steal, don't cheat. Behave decent.

I regularly update the General Instruction and News.

Expected impact of IIB

Increase in the capacity of risk taking by people: max 35% of people can accept risk, and IIB may multiply those to 70%

Raise in the number of emerging technologies: since that is one of the key targets, then by 65%, considering the inertia

Disruption of mediators between and among professionals: 0% of HR involvement is required

Emergence of more conscious and stable collaborations with solid visions: 60% of growth in this will be a success

Larger number of organically self-organizing hybrid-knowledge initiatives: since high-performers comprise only 20% of the population in an enterprise, and we will make them more visible to each other and to evt. 20% of high-performers among independent professionals, and spectrum, the chances for emergence of radical innovation may increase up to 75%

And that is targeting the international level.

IIB is in English and uses the principles of humor universality deduced in Humor Science. Most of the jokes in IIB are originally Russian as of now, but the UX participants say “The humor was too American...”

I am glad. Very glad. Bond, James Bond. Damme, Van Damme, Claude Van Damme, Jean-Claude Van Damme.

TEAM Wise Jester

Anna Zaytseva, founder: IIB concept, humor work, logic, contents, communication, fundraising

Alexey Egoshin, web developer: user interface, human-computer interaction

Massimo Stella, advisor: experiments, psycholinguistics

Rock music, style: inspiration

Uniqueness of the competence of the core team

The founder of Wise Jester, born 2019, **Anna Zaytseva**, born 1987, has been working on the IIB concept for 11 years. I received a PhD in **Management of Information Systems** for that purpose and worked with content development at an innovation-support center for social welfare solutions in South Norway. I am building IIB as a **Complex System**. I have a certificate from the **Complex Systems Summer School** at the Santa Fe Institute, a master's degree in **International and European Relations** and an honors specialist degree in **Jurisprudence**. I am the brain and engine of the IIB development.

The web developer **Alexey Egoshin** holds a PhD in **Mathematical Modelling**, a patent in **chaos simulation**, more than 12 years of experience in **web engineering**, and a portfolio of **collaborative projects** with companies from the USA, Europe, Canada and Israel. The projects include a web platform for optimizing recruitment and branding, game strategies, and a web platform for trading on financial markets. He has been working with me on IIB until now from September 2020.

The advisor **Massimo Stella** holds a PhD in **Complex Systems Simulations** and post-doc experience in **Data Science**. He is a founder of **Complex Science Consulting**, and a lecturer at the University of Exeter. Massimo does **psycholinguistics** and cognitive experiments in **change of mindsets** when people transfer from one knowledge area to another by **collaboration** or **individual choice making**. With Massimo, we did a psycholinguistic experiment and pitched it at TEDx Arendal, exhibition.

wisejester@intellectualandimmaterialbank.com

**LOOKING FOR INVESTORS AND
CO-FOUNDERS**

<https://intellectualandimmaterialbank.com>

*Cordially,
Anna A. Zaytseva,
Founder of Wise Jester AS*